

Lipid Assessment in Diabetic Patients in Karbala Hospital: A Cross-Sectional Study

Saleh Abed Alwahed Mahdi

Food Science Department, College of Agriculture, University of Karbala, Iraq

Aqeel H. Atallah

Food Science Department, College of Agriculture, University of Karbala, Iraq

Suggested Citation

Mahdi, S.A.A. & Atallah, A.H. (2024). Lipid Assessment in Diabetic Patients in Karbala Hospital: A Cross-Sectional Study. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 2(5), 296-300. DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2024.2\(5\).30](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2024.2(5).30)

Abstract:

One of the most prevalent illnesses, diabetes is not transmissible from an infected individual to a healthy one because it is present in every nation on Earth, including Iraq. Hyperglycemia is characterized by problems in the metabolism of proteins, lipids, and carbohydrates in addition to persistent hyperglycemia. The glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c) level has to be 6.5% in order to satisfy the diabetes diagnostic requirements. This study examined the relationship between high lipid levels and type 2 diabetes. The investigation's goal was to look at the connection between blood

lipid levels and blood sugar levels. Furthermore, therapy and early identification of lipid abnormalities in individuals may lower the chance of atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease. In hospitals located in Karbala, Iraq, this cross-sectional observational research was carried out between January and June of 2024. Four hundred patients between the ages of twenty-five and sixty-five were chosen for this reason. Blood glucose, triglycerides, total cholesterol, high-density lipoprotein cholesterol, low-density lipoprotein cholesterol, and glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c) were all assessed.

Keywords: *Lipid profile, Diabetes mellitus, HbA1c, cholesterol.*

Introduction

Common Metabolic Disorder Important characteristics for the early diagnosis of diabetes include absolute or relative deficiencies in insulin synthesis and/or release, which are linked to aberrant protein, lipid, and carbohydrate metabolism and chronic hyperglycemia (Dilworth, et al. 2021). Numerous research suggest that the high incidence of diabetes is largely caused by body fat, out of all body components (Unalacak, et al. 2011).

Previous studies have looked at the connection between blood lipid profile characteristics and blood glucose levels (Khan et al. 2008). Essential

hypertension, hypercholesterolemia, insulin resistance with compensatory hyperinsulinemia, and type 2 diabetes were identified as components of a multifactorial metabolic disorder in 1988 (Reaven & Banting, 1988). The World Health Organization and the International Diabetes Federation (IDF) refer to all of these conditions together as the "metabolic syndrome" (Zimmet, et al. 2005). Known medically as diabetic dyslipidemia, the condition is typified by elevated triglycerides, reduced HDL, and an increase in tiny, dense LDL particles. Important fat metabolism enzymes and pathways are impacted by diabetes, and these conditions are more prevalent when insulin

resistance or insufficiency exists (Taskinen, 2021).

It is well known that hyperglycemia is one of the causes of obesity and that dyslipidemia and atherosclerosis are causally related with the more rapid advancement of atherosclerosis in diabetic individuals due to changes in insulin levels (Regmi, et al. 2009). Our aim was to investigate the association between blood glucose and blood lipid levels in order to test the idea that treating lipid abnormalities early may minimize the incidence of cerebrovascular accidents and atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease in patients with diabetes.

Materials and Methods

Research Framework

Cross-sectional study was done in Karbala, Iraq. The clinical information of the newly diagnosed patients was retrospectively collected from their medical records using the random sample technique. Patient information was collected between January 2023 and June 2024.

Quantity of Samples

The odds ratio from an earlier study was used to determine the sample size (Alzahrani et al. 2019). 304 was the bare minimal sample size based on the procedures described in Hulley's 2007 book.

Variables of Study

The lipid profile of the diabetes patients, comprising their blood glucose, total cholesterol, high- and low-density lipoprotein cholesterol, triglyceride, and glycated hemoglobin levels, was one of the dependent variables in the study. The HbA1c values of each patient were the study's independent variables. The investigation's criteria included the patients' additional features, including blood glucose levels, age, and gender.

Analysis of Statistical Data

The statistical software for social science, SPSS version 23, was used to enter and analyze the data. Nominal and ordinal data were characterized using descriptive statistics like frequencies and percentages, while numerical

variables were defined using computations of mean, median, standard deviation, and range.

Total cholesterol, triglycerides, low-density lipoprotein cholesterol, high-density lipoprotein cholesterol, and glycated hemoglobin levels were the continuous variables in each of the four regression models. The study included gender, age, glucose level (mg/dL), and HBA1C (mg/dL) as independent variables (IVs).

Results

The number of study participants, both male and female, is listed in Table No. 1 and is broken down into five age categories. This is due to the large range of outcomes, particularly in those over forty, as well as to make statistical research easier.

Table 1. List the Characteristics of the Research Subjects (Clinically Diagnosed Patients in Karbala, Iraqi Hospitals) from January 2023 to June 2024

Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Female	285	71.25
male	115	28.75
Age		
25-35	87	21.75
35-45	137	34.25
45-55	84	21
55-65	46	11.5
65 and above	46	11.5

Since there were 400 participants in this study between January and June of 2024, data from hospitals in Karbala was integrated. In this study, the proportion of female participants was the greatest at 71.25%. The age range of 35 to 45 years included around 34.25% of the entire patient population.

Compared to people with pre-diabetes, individuals with diabetes had greater levels of triglycerides, total cholesterol, and low-density lipoprotein cholesterol. Among the research participants, there was a statistically significant correlation found between average triglycerides, low-density lipoprotein cholesterol, and

glycemic control levels. It was shown that glycemic control and the average value of high-density lipoprotein cholesterol were inversely correlated. This association, which shows the distribution of clinical (biochemical)

characteristics among clinically diagnosed patients who visited hospitals in Karbala, Iraq, between January and June of 2024, was not statistically significant, nevertheless.

Table 2. Distribution of the Biochemical and Clinical Indicators among the Clinically Diagnosed Patients that Came to the Karbala, Iraq, Hospitals between January and June of 2024

Biochemical parameters	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Minimum	Maximum
HbA1c				
Normal	120	30%	4%	5.8%
Abnormal (normal = below 5.8 %)	280	70%	5.9%	17.2%
glucose level				
Normal	126	31.5%	72	100
Abnormal (normal = 70-100 mg/dL)	274	68.5%	101	490
Total cholesterol				
Normal	296	74%	94	200
Abnormal (normal = less than 200 mg/dL)	104	26%	201	325
Triglyceride				
Normal	199	50.25%	58	149
Abnormal (normal = less than 150 mg/dL)	201	49.75%	153	870
HDL-C				
Normal	146	36.5%	40	72
Abnormal (normal = above than 40 mg/dL)	254	63.5%	21	39
LDL-C				
Normal	187	46.75%	50	100
Abnormal (normal = less than 100 mg/dL)	213	53.25%	101	220

Discussion

In this study, there were more women (71.25%) than males (28.75%). The study's high proportion of female participants can be explained by the characteristics of individuals admitted to hospitals, where a greater proportion of them needed medical attention.

Lipids have a crucial role in the pathogenesis of diabetes mellitus. Dyslipidemia and diabetes mellitus are two frequent metabolic disorders that are related to one another. Lipid metabolism problems have been demonstrated in patients with diabetes mellitus who also have an elevated risk of cardiovascular arteriosclerosis (Krauss, 2021). In the current study, the mean blood

levels of total cholesterol, triglycerides, and low-density lipoprotein cholesterol in diabetes patients were considerably higher than normal (Table 2). It is known that patients with cardiovascular illnesses are more vulnerable to these issues.

Numerous earlier investigations have demonstrated that insulin controls the enzymatic activity of lipoprotein lipase and cholesterol ester transfer protein, which impacts the hepatic synthesis of lipoprotein and hence aggravates dyslipidemia in diabetics. Low insulin also prevents the hepatic lipase production process from going through several steps, which results in the physiologically active lipoprotein lipase (Atalah et al. 2022; Mooradian, 2021).

Artha et al. (2019) found that among patients with inadequate glycemic control, there was a significant increase in triglycerides and low-density lipoprotein cholesterol. The study included 140 patients. The results of the research that was supplied had a negative correlation with high-density lipoprotein cholesterol, which was the only finding in our analysis that was not statistically significant.

An alternate explanation for the function of lipid ratios and profiles as predictive markers for glycemic management is provided by this study. It provides a lipid ratio cutoff value that diabetics may use as a new, helpful ratio to track their lipid levels in addition to illustrating the link between lipid markers. Bias may have an effect on glycemic control in individuals with diabetes mellitus as a result of the study's limitations, which include a lack of information on dietary consumption, physical activity, and diabetic comorbidities that cannot be fully addressed. Furthermore, because the current study is purely retrospective, its causal relationship is not as strong as it would be in a cohort study.

Conclusion

According to the current study, a sizable fraction of individuals with diabetes also had dyslipidemia; most had elevated low-density lipoprotein cholesterol readings and abnormal values in at least one lipid parameter. Along with HbA1c, there is a statistically significant positive association between triglycerides and cholesterol. These results highlight the crucial connection between glycemic management and dyslipidemia.

Conflict of interests

No conflict of interest.

References

- Alzahrani, S. H., Baig, M., Aashi, M. M., Al-Shaibi, F. K., Alqarni, D. A., & Bakhamees, W. H. (2019). Association between glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c) and the lipid profile in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus at a tertiary care hospital: A retrospective study. *Diabetes, Metabolic Syndrome and Obesity: Targets and Therapy*, 12, 1639. <https://doi.org/10.2147/DMSO.S219417>
- Artha, I. M., Bhargah, A., Dharmawan, N. K., et al. (2019). High level of individual lipid profile and lipid ratio as a predictive marker of poor glycemic control in type-2 diabetes mellitus. *Vascular Health and Risk Management*, 15, 149–157. <https://doi.org/10.2147/VHRM.S198294>
- Atallah, A. H., Al Masoodi, N. N., & Almosawy, W. (2022). The effect of ciprofloxacin on the lipids and some liver enzymes in albino mice. *Iranian Journal of Ichthyology*, 9, 176–179. <https://doi.org/10.22034/iji.v9i2.603>
- Dilworth, L., Facey, A., & Omoruyi, F. (2021). Diabetes mellitus and its metabolic complications: The role of adipose tissues. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 22(14), 7644. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms22147644>
- Hulley, S. B. (2007). *Designing clinical research*. Lippincott Williams & Wilkins.
- Khan, S. R., Ayub, N., Nawab, S., & Shamsi, T. S. (2008). Triglyceride profile in dyslipidaemia of type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Journal of the College of Physicians and Surgeons Pakistan*, 18(5), 270–273. <https://doi.org/10.2008/jcpsp.270273>
- Krauss, R. M. (2004). Lipids and lipoproteins in patients with type 2 diabetes. *Diabetes Care*, 27(6), 1496–1504. <https://doi.org/10.2337/diacare.27.6.1496>
- Mooradian, A. D. (2009). Dyslipidemia in type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Nature Clinical Practice Endocrinology & Metabolism*, 5(3), 150–159. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncpendmet1066>
- Reaven, G. M. (1988). Role of insulin resistance in human disease. *Diabetes*, 37(12), 1595–1607. <https://doi.org/10.2337/diab.37.12.1595>
- Regmi, P., Gyawali, P., Shrestha, R., Sigdel, M., Mehta, K. D., & Majhi, S. (2009). Pattern of dyslipidemia in type-2 diabetic subjects in Eastern Nepal. *Journal of Nepal Association for Medical Laboratory Sciences*, 10(1), 11–13.

Taskinen, M. R. (2002). Diabetic dyslipidemia. *Atherosclerosis Supplements*, 3(1), 47–51. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1567-5688\(02\)00004-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1567-5688(02)00004-9)

Unalacak, M., Kara, I. H., Baltaci, D., Ozgur, E., & Bucaktepe, P. G. E. (2011). Effects of Ramadan fasting on biochemical and hematological parameters and cytokines in

healthy and obese individuals. *Metabolic Syndrome and Related Disorders*, 9(2), 157–161. <https://doi.org/10.1089/met.2010.0100>

Zimmet, P., Alberti, G., & Shaw, J. (2005). A new IDF worldwide definition of the metabolic syndrome: The rationale and the results. *Diabetes Voice*, 50(3), 31–33.